

Poetry Reading Ability of Students in Developing Poetry at Elementary School Bontokamase, Gowa District

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Abstract:- The ability to Read Poetry at Class VA Students at UPTD Bontokamase Elementary School, Gowa Regency in Developing Makassar Language. Gowa Regency has various types of tribes, races and religions as well as customs and languages, but that is not an obstacle in uniting the people in the land of Gowa. The aims of the study were 1) to describe the poetry reading ability of the Va grade students at Bontokamase Elementary School, Gowa Regency, and 2) to improve the poetry reading skills of the Va grade students at Bontokamase Elementary School, Gowa Regency in reciting the array of each poem provided.

This research used descriptive quantitative method. Quantitative research methods can be interpreted as research methods based on natural object conditions, because researchers act as key instruments (Sugiyono, 2015: 24).

The results of research on students' ability to read poetry can be described as follows: 1) for Aska participants by reciting stanza 1 very clearly and enthusiastically, the voice is very good in front of the researcher so that assessor 1 gives score 4, assessor 2 gives value 3 and assessor gives score 2, score 3.33, total 83.33 Very good. Furthermore, Sifa participants by reciting verse 2 very clearly and enthusiastically, the voice is very good in front of the researcher so that assessor 1 gives a score of 4, assessor 2 gives a value of 3 and the assessor gives a score of 2, a score of 3.33, a total of 83.33 Very Good, while 3) Naira participants, by reciting stanza 1 very clearly and enthusiastically, the voice was very good in front of the researcher so that evaluator 1 gave a score of 4, evaluator 2 gave a value of 3 and the assessor gave a score of 2, a score of 3.33, a total of 83.33 Very good, and 4) Patir participants by reciting stanza 1 very clearly and enthusiastically, the voice is very good in front of the researcher so that assessor 1 gives score 4, assessor 2 gives value 3 and assessor gives score 2, score 3.33, total 83.33 Very good.

Keywords:- Ability, Poetry, Reading, Developing, Elementary School.

I. INTRODUCTION

The main goal of a SWT is always to maximise the power captured from the wind. It is also vital to ensure that the protection of the turbine is not compromise dinany circumstances. Thus, a power management is a very significant aspect of a wind turbine use.

Elementary school student is the forerunner in the use of language, especially Makassar language. Gowa Regency has various types of tribes, races and religions as well as customs and languages, but that is not an obstacle in uniting the people in Gowa. As a means of unity is language, in this case the regional language of Makassar. If the local language is not maintained in everyday life or at school, then we will lose the regional language as a means of communication and culture (Phillipson, 2001).

People do not only speak Makassar, but they also need preservation and maintenance so that they are accustomed in using Makassar language. The researcher intends to collaborate through poetry in the Makassar regional language (Burhanuddin & Arham, 2017). Since with Makassar language literature, children will make Makassar people who maintain and preserve as well as foreign languages, but they also like literature in the regional language (Makassar) (Urry & Walsh, 1981). Literature, especially poetry is essentially not just for broadcast, but students can understand the benefits of literature, especially Makassar regional poetry, because it uses the Makassar regional language which contains moral and religious and ethical messages. For that reason, poetry can be positioned as a literary work so that it is related to life and the learning process takes place. Thus, unwittingly literature is part of a science. Literature is what will be useful for life, especially as a student (Rahman, 2019).

To achieve this goal, many teaching techniques are considered better. One of them read poetry containing morality and religion in the Makassar regional language. However, the obstacle faced was the presence of students from other regions.

In addition, apart from being based on ethnic origin, the researcher also chose based on pronunciation, gestures, expressions. Poetry is a literary work that needs to be preserved for the younger generation. In addition, the language used is the regional language of Makassar which is included in it and also needs to continue to be used so that it does not become extinct along with the development of a multilingual population (Rahman & Sadik, 2018;

Hasnia et al., 2022). The approach to be used is an artistic approach because in poetry is not just writing, pledges of allegiance but rather messages that contain religious values that need to be preserved through performances or actions which are called poetry.

This thought inspired the researcher to conclude that as an elementary school student, language competence and poetry appreciation are inseparable. Appreciation of poetry in question is how students are able to appreciate, understand, evaluate, and produce the sound of poetry as a literary work properly. The achievement of learning outcomes or appreciation in question is of course supported by the implementation of the learning process. Implementation of learning in the classroom is carried out with various approaches, methods, strategies, which are innovative, creative, interesting so that the achievement of learning outcomes can be maximized and meaningful. One method that will be developed is thematic learning.

This research is based on the premise that to improve students' ability to read poetry, a technique that prioritizes imagination skills is needed by training the ability to preserve Makassar language culture. The ability to read a student is of course based on the ability to express ideas, thoughts and feelings through linguistic elements so that what you want to convey to listeners can be achieved.

Gowa Regency Elementary School has 2 class groups, namely morning and afternoon classes (Class A and B), class I to class VI. In this study, the class that was used as the sample was class Va, with a total of 40 students. Regarding data collection, this SD already has facilities/studios for creativity called Studio Kreasi and this place was used as a place to perform art and collect data, for the reason that it was the forerunner in the development of Makassar language poetry. Based on the observations of researchers, students / clone respondents were very happy and loved poetry in the Makassar language while second day November 5 2022 in class Va.

As seen in this photo, the class was given initial observations to see and observe the ability to read poetry in class Va. Based on the observations of researchers, students / clone respondents were very happy and loved poetry in the Makassar language. Day three of November 6 2022 in class Va.

Fig. 1: Photo during poetry reading practice

The photo above shows the scene during the practice of reading regional language poetry and the researcher guided, gave examples and corrected when there was an error in pronouncing.

II. RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

The objective of this research are 1) to describe the poetry reading ability of the Va grade students at Bontokamase Elementary School, Gowa Regency, and 2) to improve the poetry reading skills of the Va grade students at Bontokamase Elementary School, Gowa Regency in reciting the array of each poem provided.

III. LITERARY REVIEW

Literary works since the past until now have become the most interesting reading book because it is more diverse, innovative and colorful (Surya et al., 2017; Andini, 2017). The development of literary works from time to time always offers its own charm and interest for its lovers.

According to Finnegan, (2018) poetry is a literary work that shortened, and rhythmic language with a coherent sound and a selection of figurative or imaginative words. Poetry is a text that expresses the thoughts and feelings of the poet by prioritizing the beauty of words (Sahib & Rahman, 2021). In poetry, it can express various things, such as longing, anxiety, or exaltation which you express in beautiful language (Matnazarovna, 2021; Adinda et al., 2022).

While Reading poetry is an effort to convey the poet's message to listeners. Therefore, the reader must know in advance whether the message is loud or soft (Rahman, 2018; Nahdhiyah et al., 2022). With these activities, what is intended and felt by the poet is controlled by the reader.

Besides speech clarity, another vocal criterion is pause. Pauses must be arranged appropriately so that the poetry reading can be maximized (Petrey, 2016). The reader must pay attention to when it is right to take a breath and how long it takes (Bakker, 2018).

Furthermore, intonation is the rise and fall of a sentence. Intonation functions as a form of sentence meaning (Soltic, 2014). According to Rumsey, 2015 articulation is the correct pronunciation of vowels and consonants when reading poetry.

IV. METHOD

This research used descriptive quantitative method by using numbers the researcher only wants to see the ability in reading poetry for each student the researcher pays attention to how to pronounce it in Makassar language. Furthermore, the rater gives a number then the researcher describes it in words. Quantitative research methods can be interpreted as research methods based on natural object conditions because researchers act as key instruments (Sugiyono, 2015: 24).

This quantitative descriptive research focuses on the ability to read poetry in class VA of SD Negeri Bontokamase Sungguminasa, Gowa Regency. In this study, variables are defined as anything that will become the

object of research observation. In general, variable is the object that will be used as research, both abstract and real. The implementation of this activity must be systematic and in accordance with scientific principles. So, the results of observations can be justified. The theoretical basis used also affects the results obtained. The number of variables is not specified, but it depends on the type of research to be carried out.

A. Research design

Research design is a guide in carrying out the research process including in determining data collection instruments, determining samples, data collection and data analysis. This research used a descriptive quantitative method to describe the students' ability to read poetry in Elementary School Negeri Bontokamase Sungguminasa, Gowa Regency naturally as it is.

Sukmadinata (2017: 73) stated that quantitative descriptive research is intended to describe and describe existing phenomena, both natural and human-made and it pay more attention to characteristics, quality, interrelationships between activities.

B. Research Locations

This research was conducted in class Va SD Negeri Bontokamase Sungguminasa, Gowa Regency with a total of 40 students consisting of 20 males and 20 females from the entire population. The school is one of the leading schools in Gowa Regency. There are 4 poetry participants, namely 1) Aska, b) Sifa, c) Naira, and 4) Patir.

C. Research Instruments

The instrument used the format for assessing students' ability to read poetry individually. Djumingin (2011: 117) provides things that need to be considered in assessing poetry reading ability as follows:

No	Evaluation	Criteria				
1	Pronunciation	A	B	C	D	E
2	Intonation	A	B	C	D	E
3	Gesture	A	B	C	D	E
4	Appreciation	A	B	C	D	E

Table 1: Evaluation

Information : A : Very good B : Good C : Enough D : Less E : Very Less

D. Data collection technique:

Data collection was carried out using observation techniques, 1). assessment of research locations, 2). assessment of objects 3). Application for permission from the principal and class teacher Va, 4). assessment of school facilities and infrastructure, 5) the manufacture and installation of banners for this research can be seen in the photo.

To complement the results of this research, the researcher completes with photographs outside the classroom, namely on the educational stage. As seen in this photo, initial observation is given in the class to see and observe the ability to read poetry.

The research data analysis technique was carried out by: First, the researcher added up the values of the Respondents abbreviated as R based on the results of the assessment instruments used and then divided by the number of respondents based on the following table with the following formula:

$$Me = \frac{\sum xi}{n}$$

Me = Mean(average)

Xi = Value X to I to n

n = Number of individuals

Fig. 2: A photo showing a poetry reading gesture

V. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Several verses of Makassar language poetry and how to pronounce them are shown in the table below:

Makassarese	Pronunciation
Aba, bapak, mangge, tetta, akba, dan bakba	Bapakku anggappai jamaang, manggeku niakmi antoaka, Tettaku nakioka angganre Akba kemaie ammakku? Bakbaku attinroi ri ballak
aknannungang, maknannungan, ak-Pakmannannungang, ampakmannannungang,	Paralluki tappa maknannungang Kisipakmannungangi mole-mole Ammantangi ampakmannannungang
Aci, labuk; tepung, labuk lame kayu	Ammakku nganre labuk lame kayuammakna dg.Lukmuk anganre labuk lame kayu
Beradu Peraduan	Tinro (KK) (at-) attinro, mae maki attinro Ammakku ammalli katinroang
Adu, beradu Silappo, situmbuk	Silappoi otona Pak Kadir, situmbuki mobilna Pak Ali
Akhadiat, kasekreang	Paralluki niak kasekreanta
Ahkam, hukkung, atorang, undang-undang	Paralluki massing niak ki ri atoranga
Ahlan, wa sahlam Salamak	Ahlan wasahlam puang, karaeng, guru
Akidah, akedah Katappakkang	Pakabajiki akedahta ri Allah Taalah
Akil, caraddeek	Punna erokki Caraddek appilajarakki
Akang, kakak, daeng	Kisareak doekta Daeng
Akan Akan, allak Balinna (4)	Ammakku Buntingi kakakngku siayang balinna ri bangnia
Akhirukalam, pannongko kana	Sikamma mine kupabattuangki mange ri katte ngaseng.....
Aklul, patanna	Ganayya anne panna Dg.Kalu
Akil baliq Tau runka	Anak bayina Dg Bani,Tau runka
Bapak, bapak, mangge	Dasi-dasi manggeku gassing-gassing ji
Barangkali, nakulle, kapang	Tena nabattu kapang gurungku ka bosu. Ri subua Nakulle tenai bapakku ka bosu
Bawab, pajaga pekkebuk, timungang	Teako kalarroi bawabka (pajaga timunganga)
Ke bawah naung (22)	Erangi naung jamannu Baso
Arung/bunyi, suara, gemuruh	Niak sa'ra ammarrung//am//
Aru, ikrar, janji sumpah	Pasukanga akjanji, anggaru mange ri rajayya
Arusuk, arus, harus, halal, rela	Punna eroko salama, arusuk pinawang
Asak, as, poros	Anjo tukanga appareki as ri ri tampakna
Asalak, raba, resek, gerayang	Asalaki doekta ri saksanga
Aseng, semua	Berasakta aseng enne e
Asi, hormat, mengerti adat	
Jempolok, jempol	Jempolok napake annarima gaji.(92) Jirong Basang
Jepa, sejenis kue dadar biasa terbuat dari singkong	Ammakku appareki kanrejawa jepa subangni
Jepek, lunak lembek, bubur	Maeki angganre jepek
Jerak, kubur	Bapakku appareki jeruk
Joak, pasukan	Niaki pasukanga akbundu
Jibaku, nekat, bunuh diri	Nasabak matesiriki berjibakumi
Joja, sibuk	Jojai amboyai anakna Dg.Ali
Jokjo, tunjuk	Punna attahiyyaki panjojok lima kananta anjokjo
Juku' langga, ikan bakar asaf	Bapakku ammalli jujuk' langga

Table 2: Poetry and its pronunciation

Several selected Makassarese poetry titles were used as training tools for this research along with their translations as shown below:

Makassarese	Translation
manna kere-kere mae punna ajjalak nasare	Even if it's death and destiny everywhere
bombang tamparang butta pakkuburang tonji	Even sea waves can be a grave too
manna kere-kere mae jai sikolah nipassikolai	Although everywhere, many schools are occupied by schools
sd bontokamse ji paling kungai	It's just SD Bontokamase that I like
manna tinggi kalukua assingtinggi layang-layang	Even though the height of the coconut tree is the same as the height of a kite
kuambi tonji punna sirik latappelak	I also climb if there will be embarrassment
manna jai barang-barang	Even though there are lots of treasures
doek mattepak-tepak	Money in baskets
tena bajikna punna tena sikolata	It's not good if you do not have knowledge
sassalak lalangnga tunggunna	Regret was not from the start waiting
tena memang nariolo ribokotompi manjinak mappilannassi	Not really from the start, but from behind it will become overcast, and pensive.

Table 3: Makassar Bugis poetry titles

This data is the ability to read poetry in the Va grade students of this Elementary School, totaling 40 people, with details of 20 men, 20 women who participated in poetry, 4 people. The results regarding students' ability to read poetry can be presented as follows.

Evaluator1						
Respondent	Evaluator			Score mean	%	Category
	1	2	3			
Aska	4	3	3	3,33	83,33	Very Good
Sifa	4	3	3	3,33	83,33	Very Good
Naira	4	3	3	3,33	83,33	Very Good
Patir	4	3	3	3,33	83,33	Very Good

Table 4: Evaluator

Based on the table data above, it can be described that the four students above, by going through a fairly rigorous training process, they obtained results with an average score of 83.33% in the very good category. Furthermore, by being trained by three trainers, one of whom is the researcher and teacher at the elementary school.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This research wants to increase the use of regional languages (Makassar) by using poetry as a tool to help researchers realize the objectives of this research. This research was conducted because of the concerns of researchers about the extinction of regional languages because nowadays few people use regional languages in their daily lives. Therefore, researchers seriously conduct this research in elementary schools.

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